

Lowering barriers to cultural participation through larp and larp-adjacent practices

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D4.3. – February 2026

**Funded by
the European Union**

Deliverable information

Project acronym	Larpocracy
Project no.	101177307
WP	4
Deliverable title	Lowering barriers to cultural participation through larp and larp-adjacent practices
Deliverable type	R — Document, report
Version	v.3
Date	27-02-2026
Responsible partners	University of Greenwich
Authors	J. Lopes Ramos, P.J. Maravala, J. Harper, C. E. Pires, W. Z. Szatkowska
Dissemination level	Public

Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Changes
v1	21-02-26	J. Lopes Ramos, P. J. Maravala, J. Harper, C. E. Pires, W. Z. Szatkowska	Preparation of initial draft
v2	24-02-26	As listed above.	Internal reviewer comments (A. Waern, S. Barthoma, E. Diakolambrianou).
v3	27-02-26	As listed above.	Report finalised by authors

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This research was conducted under the Horizon Europe project ‘Larpocracy: Developing Spaces for Deliberation and Democratic Skills through Role-Playing’ (101177307). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to the author(s) at: (j.ramos@greenwich.ac.uk)

Cite as

Lopes Ramos, J., Maravala, P.J. Harper, J., Pires C.E. and Szatkowska, W.Z. (2026). ‘Lowering barriers to cultural participation through larp and larp-adjacent practices’. *Larpocracy – WP4*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18823127

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About the project - Larpocracy

Larpocracy researches spaces for deliberation and democratic skill building through live-action roleplaying (larp). Funded by Horizon Europe, seven leading partners study the use of larp as a method for creating inclusive and democratic social spaces, both online and offline.

Our mission is to investigate the potential of live-action role-playing (larp) and larp-adjacent practices as methods to foster democratic skill building and political engagement. Our research aims to leverage innovative form of co-creative and embodied play to address declining engagement in traditional democracy and the limitations of social media in fostering civic discourse. The project produces:

- Studies and experiments chartering capacities of larp in supporting democratic engagement and fostering democratic skill-building.
- Public events in collaboration with designers and organisers from marginalised and vulnerable communities.
- Design exemplars of larp and larp spaces capable of supporting inclusivity and democratic engagement.
- Evidence-based Democracy by Design Toolkit.
- A widespread community of Experts understanding the capacities of larp and larp-like spaces in fostering democratic engagement.
- Evidence-based Policy Recommendations supporting policymakers in multiple domains.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to extend our sincere thanks to the staff at the Federal University of Pará in Belém for hosting the DRIFT residency. We also wish to thank the team of practitioners who supported the facilitation of DRIFT, including Alessandro Giovannucci and Fuoco Balduzzi from Chaos League; ZU-UK practitioners Bruno Emiliano, James Turpin, Alastair Eilbeck and Alice Motta; Belém based artist researchers Marina Motta, Socorro Lima, Rô Colares; and Brazilian larp company Confraria das Ideias, represented by Leandro Godoy and Thomaz Barbeiro.

With regard to the preparation of the Work Package 4 Report, we are extremely grateful for the feedback of our colleagues Annika Waern and Soner Barthoma from Uppsala University and Elektra Diakolambrianou from Larpifiers.

Executive summary

This report documents the activities of Work Package 4 within the Larpocracy project, focusing on the DRIFT artist residency and a public-facing programme of performance in Belém, Brazil, in the lead-up to, and during, COP30 in November 2025. Work Package 4 investigates how larp and larp-adjacent artistic methods can contribute to lowering barriers to participation in democratic and civic processes, particularly for communities who may not typically engage with formal deliberative structures.

Across the DRIFT programme, local artists developed and presented a diverse range of participatory works that foregrounded relational interaction, sensory engagement, and instruction-based participation. Rather than prioritising performative modes of presentation, many of the projects created structured environments in which audience-participants were invited to negotiate proximity, trust, coordination, and care in real time. This shift from spectatorship towards facilitated relational encounter emerged as a consistent feature across the works.

Audience responses indicate that participation was most accessible when clear but flexible instructional frameworks were provided. Participants reported that carefully calibrated constraints helped to scaffold confidence, particularly for those unfamiliar with immersive, or participatory art, formats. At the same time, moments of ambiguity or relational difficulty often generated productive reflection, prompting participants to adjust their behaviour in relation to others. These micro-negotiations can be understood as embodied democratic practices, including listening, compromise, and mutual attunement.

The COP30 context significantly shaped the conditions of presentation and reception. In the lead-up to the conference, local audience dynamics in Belém were influenced by both heightened global attention and local concerns regarding infrastructural pressure and uneven distribution of the benefits of such an event. During COP30 itself, the density of parallel programming required a distributed engagement strategy. By working through multiple institutional and community partners including the Federal University of Pará, the British Council, UNLIMITED, Museu das Amazônias, and Gasômetro, the DRIFT programme was able to reach both local and international audiences beyond the artists' immediate networks.

Evidence from the DRIFT residency suggests that lowering barriers to participation does not require the removal of structure, but rather the careful design of accessible entry points, clear invitations, and supportive relational frameworks. The findings indicate that larp and larp-adjacent practices can create inclusive spaces for civic reflection when they balance guidance with participant agency and attend closely to the affective and sensory dimensions of engagement. These insights will inform the ongoing development of the artistic methods that are being explored within Work Package 4 and contribute to investigations throughout the Larpocracy project into how artistic practices can support more inclusive democratic participation.

1. Introduction

This report examines how larp and larp-adjacent practices may lower barriers to cultural participation. Through discussions of role-play, and instruction-led methods of participatory performance, we consider how cultural events may be made increasingly accessible for people who may face forms of marginalisation. The findings of this report have been produced by a team that combines academic researchers from University of Greenwich and Uppsala University with artistic practitioners of ZU-UK, an immersive theatre and participatory performance company, based in London. Our insights contribute to the wider aims of the Larpocracy project which are focused on applying the creative tools of larp for democratic skill-building, fostering political engagement, and developing inclusive spaces for participation in political decision-making.

Our research in Work Package 4 of the Larpocracy project proceeds from the premise that participation in cultural activities and political processes is not equally accessible for all people. Myriad forms of privilege and disadvantage make it more, or less, feasible for individuals and social groups to take part in forms of decision-making that affect their lives. By the same token, we recognise that the possibility of offering equal access to participatory cultural events is by no means a given. Instead, producers of cultural experiences must actively seek to facilitate equitable opportunities for participation if they wish to lower the inevitable barriers that impede people from taking part. Consequently, our investigations are focused on how the methods of larp, and similar performance forms that we refer to as *larp-adjacent*, might enable artists to create works that are accessible to participation and supportive of democratic cultural engagement.

By way of definition, larp can be understood as a form of cultural expression that combines the creative agency of the artists who design the work and the participants who bring the work into existence through their role-play:

Guided by rules, participants portray fictional characters in a shared imaginary world. Larps are created by larp designers, who craft the fictional setting, set the theme, structure the event, oversee the character creation, and provide the rules for interaction and safety. The participating players are co-creators of the work who have significant autonomy and agency within boundaries set by the characters they portray, the setting, and the rules. (Koljonen et al., 2026, p.10)

We conceive larp-adjacent practices as being similar to larp in the prioritisation of participation and interaction between the people who enact the activity, but different in the degree of importance placed on character-based role-play in a fictional setting. Larp-adjacent practice may include a layer of fiction that separates the activity from everyday life, and participants may be invited to take on roles that diverges from their personal identities, but there will tend to be less requirement for fully fledged character role-play that drives the participatory action. Instead, we see larp-adjacent practice as a form of participatory performance that is characterised by instruction-led activity, through which artistic facilitation guides the progression of the event.

Our method in pursuing the research agenda outlined above is the design and facilitation of an artistic residency called DRIFT which invites interdisciplinary groups of artists to develop individual projects whilst working as a collective over an intensive period. DRIFT is a residency format that has been developed by the artists of ZU-UK (formerly Zecora Ura Theatre and Pará Active), over a 20-year period. The core features of DRIFT are a focus on rapid iteration and testing of work, an emphasis on facilitating interactions between audience-participants (rather than performance for conventional spectators) and a commitment to collective development of work, whereby artists support their peers through ongoing shared reflection and feedback (ZU-UK, 2017).

Within Work Package 4 of Larpocracy, DRIFT was undertaken as a 10-day residency in October and November 2025 in the city of Belém in the Pará region of northern Brazil. The decision to pursue the DRIFT alongside the COP30 conference in Belém was deliberate, with a specific invitation to the artists involved that their work might seek to address themes related to local climate change impacts in the Amazon, or global climate policy. DRIFT featured an interdisciplinary group of 15 artists from a wide range of cultural backgrounds in Brazil. The artists presented an idea for a short participatory performance prior to the residency and developed the work over a week-long period in the working spaces of the University of Pará in Belém, followed by seven days of public sharings with small groups of audience-participants.

Alongside the facilitation of DRIFT, our research methods featured extensive documentation of the residency through video and photography. Within the activities being undertaken, our primary focus was to look for moments of relational connection between participants that might offer insights on how the design and facilitation of the work might be supporting, or hindering, the participation of the people involved. These moments of relational contact were subsequently selected as the topics of research interviews that invited detailed reflection on how the participants had experienced the activity in question. The research interviews have offered useful insights, which will be detailed in the subsequent sections of this report, on how the facilitation of DRIFT supported the participation of the artists, how the artists supported the participation of audience-participants who experienced their work, and how the artists self-reflected on the creative development process.

Our research methods included informal conversations with the public audiences who took part in sharings of work at the conclusion of the DRIFT, which will be reported as field observations. Importantly, though, we do not intend to set out any claims in this report that the work of DRIFT artists significantly lowered barriers to participation for audiences from marginalized backgrounds. Such arguments lie beyond the scope of this report, but it is anticipated that our provisional insights can contribute to the broader aim of researching how barriers to cultural and democratic participation may be addressed by identifying artistic strategies that make it possible for artists to create increasingly accessible participatory performance work. In the sections below, we will highlight the value of instruction-led performance that offers structure and guidance for an audience who may be relatively lacking in confidence regarding active cultural participation. We also point to the importance of shared physical movement as the basis for relational connection, suggesting that the embodied nature of

relational care may deserve more attention in facilitating democratic engagement, rather than focusing primarily on rational deliberation.

In presenting this report, our intention is for it to be read as a practical summary of the work undertaken during DRIFT and the creative insights that emerged from it. As such, our aim is not to present theoretical accounts of larp-adjacent practices or the design of democratic spaces. We acknowledge, however, that our report is strongly informed by the research of other work packages within the Larpocracy project, particularly the report of Work Package 5, which includes a comprehensive review of how democratic space may be theorised along with useful suggestions for the ways that larp festivals design for democratic participation (Koljonen et al., 2026). We view our report as being complimentary to the work of our colleagues within Larpocracy by setting out practical recommendations for facilitating cultural activities in pursuit of greater accessibility. Importantly, by expanding the disciplinary range of research beyond larp itself to include a broader variety of artistic practices, we aim to bring the insights of larp practice to an increasingly diverse audience of participatory art producers.

The report is structured in three main sections. In section 2, we set out the founding principles of how the DRIFT residency is facilitated, foregrounding the intensive time period and the immersive nature of collective group work. Having set out the approach to facilitating the residency, we move on in section 3 to provide an overview of the individual projects of the participating artists, highlighting how the residency process informed the evolution of their work. Lastly, in section 4, we offer insights emerging from the responses of audience-participants who experienced the works of DRIFT artists. This section includes discussion of our observations of public audience responses alongside more detailed accounts of how DRIFT artists reflected on taking part in the work of their peers. The report concludes with a section that summarises our emerging insights on how larp and larp-adjacent practices can lower barriers to cultural participation, focusing on the potential for instruction-led performances to provide supportive guidance for participants that encourages acts of relational care as the basis for creative deliberation and purposeful action.

2. Facilitation of the DRIFT residency

The DRIFT residency took place over a ten-day period in late October and early November 2025 in the theatre spaces of the University of Pará in Belém. It was facilitated by the artists of ZU-UK, with Artistic Director Persis Jadé Maravala taking the lead facilitator role with additional facilitation and coordination from Professor Jorge Lopes Ramos. Alessandro Giovanucci and Fuoco Balduzzi of Chaos League also facilitated sections of the residency with a specific focus on sharing methods of live action role-play design with participants. Each day within the core period of the residency followed the same essential structure: the morning session would commence with physically focused activities, followed by a creative design task; the afternoon session would feature a framework for

experimentation with allocated time for artists to work on their own projects in response to a daily set of creative restrictions, with the evening set aside for testing work-in-progress and mentoring. Alongside seven days of this working pattern, the DRIFT residency transitioned into a seven-day period of public performances that allowed artists to share their work and continue developing it in response to participant feedback.

The structure and facilitation of the DRIFT residency was deliberately designed to be intensive for the artists involved, setting a high bar for attendance and focus, with the aim of ensuring that artists could receive enough support to progress a project from initial idea to public output. In other words, taking part in the DRIFT required participants to devote all of their time over an intense period to the work of the residency. The provision of financial and accessibility support for artists lowered barriers to participation by allowing them to secure childcare, time off work, or mobility arrangements that enabled them able to attend fully. The core focus on lowering barriers to participation in performances for public audiences was retained as a central concern and the community of practitioners supported each other in pursuing this overarching aim through their ongoing participation of iterative testing and reflection on works-in-progress.

This section of the Work Package 4 report will describe how DRIFT indirectly lowered barriers to cultural participation by inviting artists to expand their knowledge and skills in facilitating participatory performance works. We will focus on the invitation for artists to move away from deliberately performative works in which their own performance role is foregrounded, in favour of work that is centres upon interactions between participants. In doing so, we consider the potential of bringing the methods of live action role-play into dialogue with theatrical forms, such as clowning. We also highlight the fundamental value of physical performance practices that invite participants to move together as the basis for developing relational connections with each other, which served as the basis for creating a temporary community of practice that allowed the DRIFT artists to continually iterate upon their creative ideas through a process of rapid design and testing.

2.1. Moving together as the basis for relational connection

As noted above, each day of the DRIFT residency commenced with the invitation for artists to engage in collective movement activities. The primary positioning of shared movement at the beginning of the working day should not be seen merely as a warm-up exercise. Instead, we see the physical movement of groups as being foundational for the promise of developing relational connections that can support collaboration, beyond verbal modes of interaction. The value of structuring relational movement together was highlighted on the first day of DRIFT in an activity that tasked the artists with forming pairs and creating portrait photographs of each other. An important aspect of this exercise was that it was conducted non-verbally, which challenged participants to develop their physical sensitivity towards unfamiliar people and forge a collaborative connection. One of the DRIFT artists, Y¹, commented on

¹ Please Note: The names of artists are replaced with pseudonyms to maintain anonymity when discussing their contributions to the DRIFT residency and research interviews.

the way that the physical preparation at the start of the day enabled her to find a physical alignment with her partner in the exercise:

Figure 1: Moving together as the basis for relational connection. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

You need to have your body stretched for what you're going to do. I'm finding it wonderful... And when you relax and let the other person move you, control you, direct you...I started moving her body, I asked her permission to let me move her body. She has some limitations in lowering and raising herself...And then I told her, do this hip movement. To relax more, loosen the hips more. I thought it was beautiful that she was still very stiff, you know. And then I managed to get her to loosen up a little more, a little bit more...And then we managed to make the movements there in the light to appear in the shadow. Notice your hand, the movement, and she managed it. That made me very, very happy to be able to get someone who was very stiff to move more... Yes, from the exchange with the other, from perceiving the other, from perceiving yourself, perceiving your body. There were moments when I did it behind her to see our two shadows merging. (Y, 2025).

As this example indicates, the process of physical stretching and preparation served as a foundation, in Y's view, for relational connection. Her partner, S, commented on this exercise, noting that she felt some initial discomfort in being manipulated by I, but she also pointed towards a preparedness to let go of fixed ideas about what the exercise should produce and accept what transpired:

She started making the movements and I understood that it was the proposal of the game and I started to follow...I think a slight disagreement of understanding, but not an internal struggle, you know? Like, I understood something different, but I'm not going to create, let's say, an energy to fight against it, you know? Because fighting isn't always healthy, right? But I didn't want to go into a fight that wasn't healthy, you know? Uh, and yes, let's live, live the experience. The experience is always an experience...So, I think that even though the command was different from what I had imagined, I had thought we would have an experience there with her, right? With her, with the command. (S, 2025).

S's reflections on the selfie exercise, in dialogue with those of Y, point towards the value of shared physical preparation in finding relaxation, not only as a physical state of ease, but also as a preparedness to accept the directions of others and let go of the requirement to control a given creative task. Clearly, S had a different interpretation of the activity than that of Y, but she was available to the movements of her partner, which allowed them both to enter into a moment of exchange and connection, despite the fact that they were communicating through an underlying

disagreement. Indeed, we suggest that this exercise created a designed discomfort that offered participants an opportunity to safely and playfully explore personal assumptions about what their body can or cannot do whilst also, potentially, expanding their perceptions of others beyond initial preconceptions. The broader insight that can be extrapolated from this account of the selfie exercise is that moving together in response to instructions or guidance can provide a strong foundation for people to form relational connections with each other, without the requirement for language to establish shared understandings. Consequently, we suggest that the basic prescription of shared movement can open fertile possibilities for relational exchange.

2.2. Game design process over performative product

Figure 2: Theatrical staging of performance work. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team

The DRIFT residency offered artists an opportunity to diversify their creative methods by experimenting with possibilities of game design and live action role-play. The focus on participatory performance forms was explicitly framed as an invitation to move away from theatrical modes of presentation in which an audience would centre their attention upon the work of performers. This shift away from performative theatricality was not an easy task, however, with some participants continuing to place themselves at the heart of the performance work, using relatively traditional staging tropes. For example, in the selfie exercise from the first day of the residency, one pairing of artists created a deliberately staged portrait of a performer singing, which prompted one of the participants, A, to reflect on her nostalgia for performance:

I'm very familiar with the stage, in general, and I'm currently experiencing a moment of rediscovering myself singing, you know, rediscovering my voice, like that. So, uh, anyway, I think the stage has always been present, even if not physically, as a desire in my life as well. So, the stage was important for her (referring to her performance persona) because she's returning to the stage. She's singing again...So that's why it was nostalgic. (A, 2025a).

Another participant, U, made similar comments about the selfie exercise, reflecting on the fact that the activity took place within a theatre setting, which made her feel the security of familiarity. She explained that: *'I'm from the theatre, right? So, I feel at home here'* (U, 2025), offering a simple and direct indication that DRIFT artists from theatrical backgrounds seemed to feel a sense of comfortable familiarity with theatrical spaces and the conventions that go with them.

Although some artists came from performative perspectives as their starting points, the workshop activities of DRIFT encouraged them to break out of familiar working routines. On the first and second days of the residency, artists were given game design tasks, using simple materials to create a playable experience. The actual content of the games created was, essentially, unimportant. Our intention in using game design activities was to prompt a transition from thinking in terms of performance to thinking in terms of playful participation, structuring and scaffolding relational engagement and exposing invisible systems of power, such as hierarchies, inequalities and cultures of exclusion. This shift was further enhanced through a workshop session on larp led by the facilitators of Chaos League, Alessandro Giovanucci and Fuoco Balduzzi. DRIFT artists were invited to play short larps and take a crash course in designing their own role-play works. The inclusion of larp within the schedule of DRIFT offered an important provocation to artists to consider how design parameters of participatory works can shape relations between participants without imposing a scripted determination of what should happen. In other words, by analysing the design of larp, the artists were encouraged to refocus their creative thinking on designing for relational connection between participants, offering guidance to shape the performance action without scripting pre-determined outcomes.

In sharing the core theory of larp, the facilitators of Chaos League emphasised the principle that larps are typically not performed for an audience. However, it should be acknowledged that, in our view, several of the DRIFT artists started their approach to the larp activities as if they were performing for an audience rather than playing to build a shared fiction with other participants. This led to a recognition that the presence of any type of observers in the play space creates the risk of returning to a theatrical paradigm that prompts participants to start performing for an audience. In later sections of this report, we will offer further discussion of certain issues that arose when players in participatory works felt the gaze of spectators. This prompted the facilitation team to make the decision, at the midway point of the DRIFT residency, that there should be no external observers when the DRIFT artists were testing their works-in-progress.

Aside from the questions relating to the presence of an audience, the work on larp design within DRIFT prompted useful reflections amongst participants about the nature of artistic authorship in participatory works. Although larp practice foregrounds the creative agency of the players who enact the role-play, we argue that this does not diminish the importance of authorship in the design of the work. In other words, the designer, or design team, can maintain clear artistic agency in constructing the parameters that shape the experience, alongside the creative agency of the participants themselves (Lopes Ramos and Maravala, 2017). This leads us to the viewpoint that the importance of player agency in participatory artworks should not be overstated. It may be tempting to conflate player agency with a sense of unbounded freedom, but we see this as a problematic approach (Lopes Ramos et al., 2020). Rather, the agency of players emerges from within the designed constraints that the artist creates.

Our suggestion that player freedom ought not to be overstated as a principal priority when designing or analysing participatory performance works should not be seen to diminish the value of participants

in the work. On the contrary, we see the provision of design parameters as a form of support that guides the people taking part. This notion of guidance may seem paternalistic or patronising, but we argue that the excessive privileging of agential freedom can be reflective of pre-existing privilege. In other words, the capacity to play with unbounded freedom is a privilege that is not shared by all players, in much the same way that equal participation in democratic spaces is necessarily hindered by myriad forms of marginalisation that prioritise some voices and exclude others. Consequently, we suggest that uncritical valorisation of agential freedom in participatory performance works may inadvertently entrench the existing privileges of those who have the greatest capacity to utilise that freedom. By contrast, the provision of design parameters that guide the experience of players may be more conducive to lowering barriers to participation for people who might not typically be able, or feel able, to express their agency freely.

2.3. Participatory performance design and the facilitation of interaction

Figure 3: Facilitating *Binaural Dinner Date*. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

An important part of the DRIFT residency was the opportunity for artists to experience some of the previous works of ZU-UK as embodied examples of instruction-based approaches to participatory performance design. In contrast with larp practices which may often provide participants with a broad space of possibility to interpret a character and determine their trajectory within the fiction, the works of ZU-UK can be understood as more closely facilitated experiences that offer a greater degree of guidance to participants on how to play. One such work is *Binaural Dinner Date* (ZU-UK, 2017-Ongoing) which features a blind date scenario, facilitated by a character that

they hear via individualised audio instructions and a live performer in a generic waiter role. The waiter tasks pairs of participants to undertake various games and playful activities as a ludic framework for their dinner date experience. Participants do not play characters, but rather a version of themselves in the imaginary circumstances of a romantic role-play. Given that *Binaural Dinner Date* clearly presents a fictional situation, but without the full provision of fictional character roles (Guillery et al., 2025), it can be understood as a *larp-adjacent* practice.

A small section of *Binaural Dinner Date* was played with three pairs of participants in an outdoor café setting in Belém. The experience of one of the pairings featured a small segment of the piece in which the waiter-facilitator asks the couple to envisage their ideal wedding, which prompted the players to develop a rapid intimacy based on their shared vision of a forest wedding featuring elf costumes. In

reflecting on this experience, one of the participants, O, commented on the possible tension between player immersion in the romantic role-play and the ongoing presence of the waiter as the facilitator:

She's asked the question and she turns to look at me and she smiles and she said, 'In a forest'...which then made me laugh because I was about to say the same thing...so yeah, I'm reacting surprised because I said - I say 'that's crazy. I was about to say the same thing'. And I'm nodding and she says, 'And they're dressed as elves'. And I laugh again because that's exactly what I was picturing. And I say, 'Yes, with fantasy clothes'. I think at that point, James' (the waiter) attention turned again. But in the last few moments, she says, 'And everyone else is stressed over us'. And then she laughed. And then we both laughed again...I'm surprised by the coincidence. It's such a - a niche answer that we both were about - well, she gave it, but I was about to give it. So, I'm surprised. And in the surprise, I get excited...She's charming. I'm charmed...She's smiling. I'm smiling...like, I'm not jumping across the table, but I'm definitely pulling my chest out a little bit more...it's like a sense of openness like I want to know more. I want to know you more...I don't think she wanted to have like a deeper chat, but like I have the feeling that she might want to say a few words. And then James starts talking again. So, he cuts her sentence. And we're laughing. But I have this - there is a moment where I feel like she was about to say something more and then the game continues. So, we shift it back to James. (O, 2025).

As this example indicates, the series of prompts from the facilitator which culminated in a suggestive invitation where players were asked to imagine their dream wedding, stimulated a strong sense of connection within the romantic role-play, but O's comments also point towards a sense of frustration that the facilitator had interrupted the moment by moving on to the next stage of the performance. This is perhaps unsurprising, given that this experience was presented in an intentionally shortened form the purposes of the residency. However, we suggest that the ongoing presence of the waiter-facilitator allowed participants to play with a sensitive subject matter like romance with the safety that comes from being reminded that their activity is play rather than actuality.

O's play partner, D, affirmed that the shared visualisation of the elf wedding in the forest produced a moment of genuine warmth and connection, describing it as *'the moment of the flames'* when she recognised O's agreement with her vision. However, she went on to say that this romantic connection was simultaneously authentic and performed: *'I was myself - like it was authentic, but it was also a little bit of acting if you understand?'* (D, 2025). O shared similar reflections, noting that *'It's not real. It's a game. But you're still asking both of us to put ourselves in a situation where we have to picture ourselves as being a couple. So, the situation itself is creating at least the pretence of intimacy or privacy or at least the request of imagining it'* (O, 2025). As these comments indicate, the chosen fragment from the experience of *Binaural Dinner Date* allowed players to develop a genuine sense of connection in a very short timeframe of 5-10 minutes whilst still maintaining a clear awareness of the fictional nature of the role-play. We suggest that the ongoing presence of a play facilitator can help maintain the boundary between fiction and reality, even if their interjections can at times cause

frustration, as they serve to remind participants that the activity they are engaged in is, ultimately, only play.

As the DRIFT residency progressed, and the artists moved towards sharing their work with public audiences, the importance of facilitation became increasingly apparent. Several artists developed works that featured their own naked, or semi-naked, bodies as focal points, with the invitation for participants to directly interact with them as the core action of the performance. Given the sensitive nature of this type of interaction, the development of the performances in question placed strong emphasis on the need for clear facilitation so that participants could engage with the work in appropriate ways. One artist, Edivânia Câmara Iyatunde² created a work based on a funeral rite that centred upon her partially naked body in the persona of Jurema, a mythical figure representing the spirit of the Amazon forest. Participants were led into the performance space one at a time and given the instruction *'Go to Jurema. She is dying. She will ask you a question. Listen to her, then write your answer on her body'*. The facilitator would then hand a pen to the participant and say, *'Once you've done that, please make physical with another person'*. This example offers clear indication of a facilitation protocol that was simple and precise. The instructions noted above, which were initially delivered by lead facilitator Persis Jadé Maravala, and later offered by other DRIFT artists, gave clear guidance to participants on what they were expected to do, whilst still leaving space for creative interpretation.

In our reflections on the facilitation of DRIFT, we see the creative process of refining facilitation instructions for participatory performance as a key opportunity for developing insights on lowering barriers for cultural participation. One area of practice that may be of particular interest in this regard is the performance genre of clowning. The DRIFT residency featured three clown artists from a variety of training backgrounds. In the early stages of the process, some of the work being developed by these artists featured standard clowning tropes focused on the delivery of physically comedic performances to please the audience. This default model of clowning adapted and changed, however, in response to our encouragement for artists to focus less on their performative relationship with an audience and more on the ways that they could facilitate relations between audience-participants themselves. One of the clown artists, Ida Luciana Delaude, worked with her performance persona Palhaça Catraca to create a performance in which she played the role of a bored professor who has to teach people about climate change despite having already given up on the possibility of achieving any positive change. Rather than focusing solely on making the audience laugh, this performance created relational discomfort by asking audience-participants to dress each other in excessively warm clothes, literally making each other sweat to induce the physical experience of global warming. This example gives a good indication of how the clown was able to re-direct her attention and the attention of audience members towards each other as participants.

² Please Note: The names of artists are included in discussions that directly relate to the public performance works that they created during the DRIFT residency.

*Figure 4: The clown Palhaça Catraca invites participants to play.
Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.*

Although the working practices of ZU-UK have not focused on clowning, the experience of working with clown artists within the DRIFT residency has prompted new ideas on the possibilities of using methods of clowning in developing facilitation for participatory performance. In contrast with the expectation that a facilitator will be competent and in control, clowns are inherently fallible, and their openness to making mistakes can open space for participants to be silly and

vulnerable as well. This capacity for clowns to become vulnerable offers scope for a shift in status whereby the facilitator can pass status on to participants rather than remaining the centre of performative attention. The image above shows Ida facilitating an early version of one of her performances as Palhaça Catraca and it gives a good indication of the way that DRIFT encourages artists to become a collective creative resource for each other.

By continually testing their work and serving as test audience members to support the ongoing development work of others, DRIFT artists established a temporary community of practice that enabled them all to produce works that could not have been created if they had developed them alone. We believe that participatory artworks, along with a wider array of cultural processes that invite public participation, cannot be developed according to the theoretical abstractions of isolated artists, designers or policy makers. Instead, the development of effective participatory work requires an interdisciplinary participatory development process that allows the maker to get continuous feedback on whether their intentions are being realised in actuality by the participants. A core principle of the DRIFT residency was that participants were expected to test their work in the evening session of every day and receive feedback from fellow artists to inform the next iteration. This process of rapid iteration and testing encourages a willingness to embrace failures as a constitutive feature of a productive working process in which a community of practice can constructively critique works-in-progress.

2.4. Summary

To summarise this section of the Work Package 4 report, the facilitation of the DRIFT residency was designed to demand a new type of focus and commitment of participating artists, in pursuit of the broader aim of lowering barriers to participation for the audience-participants who would ultimately experience their work. The daily structure culminated in an evening sharing of work that challenged artists to continually test their ideas and participate in the testing being undertaken by others. The intensity of **rapid and ongoing iteration of work** fostered a strong sense of community amongst the

participant group which was also supported by the morning movement sessions which prompted artists to use **relational movement models as a foundation for establishing relational connections** with each other.

The creative process was focused on encouraging artists to **facilitate interactions between participants** rather than foregrounding their own presence as performers. To pursue this aim, our use of game design methods, coupled with sessions on larp design, offered tangible tools for artists to design parameters that would guide participation rather than creating scripts or pre-determined performance scores. The emphasis on facilitating participation was also supported by sharing fragments of previous ZU-UK works with DRIFT artists, which allowed them to experience facilitation methods that provide **instructional guidance to participants** whilst still allowing them space for their own creative decision-making.

Importantly, the learning process of DRIFT was a two-way process in the sense that we, as a facilitation team, gained a great deal from encountering the artistic practices of a diverse range of artists. Creating a space in which all participants can learn from each other requires a sense of playfulness that allows people to brave and allow themselves to challenge preconceptions. To do those things, they also need to feel able to be vulnerable and make mistakes. The intensity of DRIFT was not built on a drive to succeed and produce works of brilliance. Rather, it came from a shared commitment to seek out **relations of mutual support** that allowed artists to try and fail, then try again and fail better. As the following section illustrates, the works that the DRIFT artists produced embodied this spirit of vulnerability that simultaneously allowed for playfulness, bravery and care.

3. DRIFT artists' projects

In this section of the Work Package 4 report, we provide an overview of the participatory performance works that were produced by artists within the DRIFT residency. While each of the projects presented in this section is distinct in aesthetic language and thematic focus, they share a set of underlying design tendencies that emerged through the DRIFT process. Across the works, we observe a consistent shift from performative display towards facilitation of relational encounters, and from fixed artistic authorship towards co-created experiences shaped by participant agency within designed constraints. These shared tendencies are particularly relevant to the core focus in Work Package 4 on lowering barriers to cultural participation.

3.1 Bath / Banha (Azeda Pororoca)

Figure 5: Azeda Pororoca in *Banha / Bath*. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

breaking as a negative experience, Azeda discussed how the invitation to treat audiences as co-creators had created a ‘*turning inside out*’ of her typical approach to performing as a clown, prompting what she described as ‘*a very close, very genuine contact*’ with participants (Pororoca, 2025).

As the image opposite illustrates, the collective act of care that the performance stimulated brought audience-participants into close proximity with each other, challenging them to negotiate the bathing ritual with sensitivity and co-operation. The ritual structure redistributed agency, transforming audience members from observers into co-authors of a collective act of vulnerability and care.

This performance centres on a communal ritual where the performer, in her persona as a clown, invites five participants to engage in a sensory experience. Guided by the clown, the group gathers in a circle to prepare a fragrant herbal bath rooted in the traditions of the Amazonian landscape.

The performance explores themes of collective participation and purification, ultimately reversing the roles of caretaker and subject. This spiritual and theatrical exchange concludes with the audience members ceremonially bathing the artist, symbolizing a shared connection through the elemental power of water.

In reflecting on her participation in the DRIFT residency, Azeda Pororoca commented that ‘*the participants have been guided to carry out our work in a more open and participatory way. So, it really opened up. We came with a proposal and it was broken, right?*’ Rather than viewing this

Figure 6: Participants enact a bathing ritual. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

Crucially, Azeda conceived the experience as a silent ritual, in which verbal communication was suspended and the only live sound present was the rhythmic pulse of a *tambor*. This sonic restraint shaped the atmosphere of the work, fostering a heightened state of attentiveness and embodied listening among participants.

Rather than relying on explicit verbal instructions or predetermined cues, the performance generated a shared sense of agency through mood, rhythm, and proximity. Within this carefully attuned environment, participants gradually intuited their role in the ritual, arriving at the act of bathing the performer, not as a task assigned, but as an emergent collective decision shaped by the affective and sensory conditions of the encounter. The work enabled relational interaction by requiring participants to coordinate care without speech, compelling them to read each other's bodily cues and negotiate shared responsibility through silence, proximity, and touch.

3.2. C.F.B.I. – Circo Federal de Brincadeiras Investigativas / Federal Circus of Investigative Games (Bruna Almeida)

Figure 7: Bruna Almeida facilitates her performance. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

This project is an immersive art installation designed to reconnect adults with their youth through the physical act of playing childhood games. Participants navigate a path of recycled materials re-used as play objects while listening to a guided audio narrative that transitions from the innocence of early childhood to the self-awareness of adulthood. By combining rhythmic physical movement with a ten-minute auditory journey, the experience encourages a recycling of thoughts and a nostalgic rediscovery of play. Ultimately, this creative intervention aims to transform public spaces into sites of emotional reflection and intergenerational connection.

The project generated relational interaction by placing participants in situations of playful tension, where cooperation and physical negotiation became necessary to complete tasks under time pressure. Through shared rule-making and collective problem-solving, the installation reframed play as a socially constructed and co-

authored experience. Using the same set of recycled materials, different teams generated divergent

game structures and rules, underscoring the open-ended nature of the installation and positioning play as an emergent, collectively authored practice rather than a fixed or predetermined form.

The image opposite is taken from the development process in which fellow DRIFT artists tested Bruna Almeida's concept. The image shows one participant attempting to play the childhood game of hopscotch while being restrained by others. This invitation for players to enter into a bodily tension with each other is suggestive of the tensions involved in participatory art projects that ask adults to be playful. In other words, the work engaged players with the difficulty of rediscovering a child-like sense of play and wonder.

Central to the interactive structure of the work was Bruna's invocation of the logic of timed competition, commonly associated with children's games. Participants were required to respond to a sequence of instructions under temporal pressure, encouraging rapid decision-making and collective problem-solving. Rather than operating as individual players, participants were compelled to gather, negotiate, and collaborate as a team to interpret and fulfil the tasks proposed by the audio narrative.

Figure 8: Playing with relational tension. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

3.3. *Refeed de Piranha / Piranha Stew* (Lu Bórges)

This project creates a participatory artistic experience centred around the intimate act of eating together. Rather than performing for an audience, the artist gathers a group of guests to collaboratively prepare a traditional fish-based stew known as piranha pirão. Using specific recipes and instructions, the piece facilitates a communal banquet that fosters connection and conversation through the shared labour of food creation.

The performance deliberately positioned the artist's body in a state of heightened vulnerability, transforming it into a receptive surface through which relations of care, control, and trust were negotiated. Initially, the artist assumed a witnessing role: observing as audio instructions prompted participants to feed one another, establishing a circuit of mutual nourishment.

Figure 9: Lu Bórges in *Refeed de Piranha / Piranha Stew*. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

As the action unfolded, pieces of shrimp were placed directly onto the artist's body, which then became an intermediary site within the ritual of feeding: participants were invited to take the food from her body and offer it to others, accompanied by the sharing of açaí. This gradual shift from the artist as observer to becoming an embodied focal point of the performance intensified the relational stakes of the encounter. The performance culminated in an instruction asking participants to tighten a corset around the artist's body after the meal, a gesture that simultaneously invoked restraint, care, and exposure. Through this sequence, the work foregrounded the ethical and affective dimensions of participatory practice, situating vulnerability not as spectacle, but as a condition co-produced and sustained by collective responsibility.

The performance activated relational dynamics by staging feeding, restraint, and bodily exposure as acts requiring negotiated trust, compelling participants to continuously recalibrate boundaries and responsibility toward one another. The shifting position of the artist's body intensified this relational field, making care and power visibly co-produced among the group.

The image below shows a phase of the performance in which the artist lies on the dining table and makes her body the site and substance for the conclusion of the meal. Participants are guided in their interactions through audio recorded instructions delivered via headphones. The image is suggestive of the high levels of trust and care that can be produced when participatory artworks foreground the artist's body as the focus for interactions between participants.

In reflecting on her participation in the DRIFT residency, Lu Bórges commented that due to the intensity of the process 'you're kind of forced to take it out of your head' which, for her, 'ignited a fire of creation'. She highlighted the value of the 'visceral' connection with a public

Figure 10: The artist's body as the focal point for participant interactions. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

audience that she had been able to create, offering a strong affirmation of artistic processes in which ‘we really expose ourselves and open up to the game’ (Bórges, 2025).

3.4. *Rimas e multi vozes amazônicas / Amazonian Rhymes and Multiple Voices (Bruno BO MC)*

This piece challenges the spirit of individualism, offering an experience that simulates the collective composition of a rap song by a group of eight lyricists (4 men and 4 women), about the "B-side" of the Amazon, providing interaction and poetic creativity among the participants.

The image opposite shows the audience participants in two rows, facing a partner, with Bruno in his traditional role as MC. As the performance unfolds, the singular voice on the mic is replaced with multiple voices as participants develop their composition.

Bruno offers participants the option of working from a pre-selected musical track, which serves as a shared rhythmic and sonic foundation for the composition process. From this common base, participants begin generating lyrics and vocal interventions, gradually moving into a phase of negotiation in which decisions are made collectively regarding what material is retained, what is discarded, and how the refrains are ordered and repeated.

Figure 11: Bruno BO MC facilitating his performance. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

Figure 12: Participants gather in a circle to share their rhymes. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

This process foregrounds collaboration not only as simultaneous creation, but as an exercise in dialogue, compromise, and collective authorship, revealing how musical structure emerges through social negotiation rather than individual expression. The piece concludes with a transition to a circle in which participants combine their respective compositions into a whole, emphasising the power of collective creation. As a whole, the piece fosters relational interaction through collective authorship, requiring participants to negotiate lyrical choices, rhythm, and structure in real time. By transforming individual

expression into collaborative composition, the work positioned dialogue, compromise, and shared rhythm as the foundation of creative connection.

3.5. Enquanto a música toca / While the Music Plays (Mariô Monteiro)

Figure 13: Mariô Monteiro facilitates her performance.
Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

their social and cultural trajectories. Through this process, the competitive logic of a childhood game is gradually displaced, transforming the experience into a collaborative and cathartic mode of musical creation. Personal memories and reflections are translated into sound, reconfiguring play as a collective practice of listening, expression, and shared affect.

Participants work in small teams to choose emotional themes and reimagine musical lyrics, which are then layered with rhythms and effects to create a cohesive musical piece. The performance turns individual voices into a shared auditory experience, fostering a sense of cultural resistance and belonging. At the conclusion of the experience, participants were confronted with a moment of surprise as a complete song, composed directly from their responses to the facilitator's questions,

This project functions as a collaborative sound work that is designed to engage underserved communities in the lead-up to COP 30 through the intersection of memory, technology, and art. The performance initially invites the public to take part in what is framed as a 'un-birthday party', without revealing that participants will ultimately be engaged in the co-creation of a musical composition drawn from their own lived experiences.

Acting as a facilitator rather than a performer, Mariô Monteiro employs the familiar structure of musical chairs, alternating music and movement with moments of pause in which participants are asked questions relating to

Figure 14: Participating in the 'un-birthday party'.
Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

Figure 15: Playing 'musical chairs'. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

was played back to them at the end of the un-birthday party. Hearing their own words transformed into lyrics allowed participants to recognise themselves as co-authors of the work, revealing retrospectively how their personal narratives had been woven into a shared musical composition. This final gesture functioned both as a celebratory closure and as an affective mirror, reinforcing the collective and reflective dimensions of the performance.

The image above illustrates the playful nature of this project, featuring a game of musical chairs within the performance. By utilising well-known party games within the piece, along with playful props like party hats, Mariô's work facilitated a celebratory mood amongst audience participants. The performance enabled relational exchange by converting individual memories into shared musical material, compelling participants to listen actively and co-create a collective sonic narrative. The reveal of the final composition reinforced participants' recognition of their interdependence in shaping the outcome. In reflecting on her experience of the participatory performance methods in the DRIFT residency, Mariô commented: *'It surprised me in the best ways. It's a type of theatre that I hadn't yet experienced, which allowed me to delve deeper into research I was already doing on how my art can be a revolutionary tool, a tool of subversion'*. She went on to suggest that her creation of *'sonic fun'* could be a new form of leisure activity for people to engage with a local culture (Monteiro, 2025).

3.6. *COMUM / COMMON* (Ester Sá)

Figure 16: Ester Sá facilitating *COMUM / COMMON*. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

This piece is delivered as an experiment about communication. Ester Sá's project invites audience-participants to engage in personal reflections alongside dialogue with others. Guided by lines of colour on the floor, simple questions and prompts for creative action offer participants opportunities to express their identities and share themselves with others.

The performance unfolded as a game-based structure in which participants were invited to align their sense of identity with that of others by selecting thematic prompts displayed on the floor. As individuals chose themes that resonated with their personal experiences, they were required to physically reposition themselves within the space, forming temporary constellations based on shared choices and affinities.

As the images below illustrate, the performance of *COMMON* charts a simple physical journey from individual to shared experience, from isolation to connection. This continuous process of movement and regrouping transformed identity into a relational and spatial practice, making visible how notions of self are negotiated in proximity to others. Through this embodied matching of identities, the work foregrounded communication as an active and performative process rather than a fixed exchange of information. The work facilitated relational interaction by requiring participants to publicly position themselves in relation to others, making identity a spatial and negotiated practice. Through repeated regrouping, the performance revealed belonging as something dynamically constructed through proximity and shared choice.

Figure17: Participants playing *COMUM / COMMON*. Photographs by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

3.7. *Despersona* (Yaci Uaruá)

This project is structured a live action role-play experience that guides participants through the emotional arc of a romantic relationship. The narrative unfolds in three distinct acts: falling in love, enduring a breakup, and finding a new beginning, to mirror the cyclical nature of human connection. Utilizing a theatre space divided into specific zones, the project emphasizes sensory immersion with the deliberate use of lighting and sound design. To conclude the journey, participants are invited to document their personal experiences through written reflection, turning their internal reflections into a shared record of the event.

Guided by audio instructions delivered through headphones, participants enter a fictional frame that requires close physical proximity, touch, and emotional projection, often with a stranger. This produced moments of heightened discomfort and bodily tension, particularly during tasks that asked participants to enact affection or conflict. However, rather than leading to withdrawal, these moments frequently became thresholds for deeper attunement. Over the course of the three acts, attention gradually shifted from performing the narrative of a romantic relationship to caring for the relational conditions of the interaction itself. The role-play structure enabled relational interaction by placing strangers in guided intimate scenarios that required attunement to physical and emotional cues. Trust emerged not from narrative fiction alone, but from participants' sustained negotiation of vulnerability and mutual care within the mediated frame.

The images opposite, taken during the development and testing phase of DRIFT residency gives an indication of the high levels of intimacy and emotional commitment to the experience that participants can arrive at, within a relatively short space of time, when supported by audio instructions that guide the action.

In reflecting on her experience of the DRIFT, Yaci Uaruá referred to the creation of a 'very *inviting space*' and commented that her spirit of experimentation was strongly supported by a sense of creative community: '*It was very good to be able to share this with so*

many other artists, fantastic and very powerful, but also to have the guidance of the people who were here collaborating with our work and giving insights on how to make this experience better every day'. She went on to suggest that this atmosphere had supported her in creating a '*safe and poetic*' space for participants to explore sensitive themes together (Uaruá, 2025).

Figure 18: Performing intimacy in *Despersona*. Photographs by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

3.8. *Escuta aqui pra você vê / Listen Here So You Can See* (Heloiza Barbosa)

Figure 19: Heloiza Barbosa facilitating her performance. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

Audio instructions delivered via headphones gave a simpler series of prompts to guide the action. This resulted in a greater sense of intimate connection between the participants and deepened the immersive quality of the experience. As the work evolved, the dramaturgy expanded to incorporate edited fragments of personal narratives from Brazilian immigrants living in the United States, which were transmitted to participants through headphones. These recorded stories introduced themes of displacement, belonging, and familial rupture, extending the domestic conflict staged at the table into a broader socio-political register. The audio instructions invited participants to converse and

This project features an immersive theatrical dinner to celebrate a baby's baptism, which is gradually derailed by a series of shocking personal revelations. The narrative structure is dictated by the intermittent crying of a baby, which serves as a recurring interruption that forces the diners to pause their conflict to provide care. The experience concludes only when the infant falls asleep, finally allowing the characters to confront the truths unmasked during the meal.

Over the course of the DRIFT residency, Heloiza Barbosa developed the piece from an initial version that featured a larger-scale family dinner party. Using a series of prompt cards, audience participants were provoked to address their personal grievances with other family members. However, the development process encouraged a paring back of the performance to focus on just two players.

Figure 20: A simplified version of the performance. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

interact in response to the cases they had heard, prompting dialogue not only about the narrated experiences but also about their own lived histories.

Through a sequence of directed questions, participants were encouraged to draw parallels between the recorded testimonies and their personal trajectories, transforming listening into an active, relational process grounded in shared vulnerability and exchange. The performance fostered relational interaction by structuring conflict and listening as shared tasks, prompting participants to respond to both fictional and real testimonies through dialogue and embodied proximity, with the reduced scale of the encounter intensifying attentiveness, making exchange more reciprocal and accountable.

3.9. *Zoom Festa da Aparelragem / Zoom Sound System Party (Socorro Lima)*

Figure 21: Socorro Lima in Zoom Festa da Aparelragem / Zoom Sound System Party. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK team.

Zoom Festa da Aparelragem is a performance based on interaction, as a sensitive, political territory. Inspired by the bodily experiences of an artist with a visual impairment (low vision), the performance addresses the body beyond the normative gaze, revealing layers of tactile, auditory, and energetic perception.

Participants were placed in a condition of restricted vision, removed from visual dominance, and required to work collectively to assemble a large-scale puzzle composed of thousands of pieces scattered across the floor. Within this environment, the artist actively encouraged participants to rely on their sensory capacities to the fullest, foregrounding touch, spatial awareness, listening, and co-operation as primary modes of engagement.

A key feature of Socorro Lima's work is the way that it highlights the experience of differently abled bodies. She commented that audiences would have the opportunity *'to see what an artistic work is like without restrictions, without comparisons, because here we have diverse bodies, but with great potential'* (Lima, 2025a)

As the image opposite illustrates, the performance uses the tools of theatrical immersion to create an atmosphere of oblique lighting, prompting audience participants to foreground their tactile engagement with the space: exploring the ground on hands and knees, feeling their way. This sensory occlusion also prompts new relations between participants as they find each other through touch. By restricting vision and requiring collective puzzle-solving, the work compelled participants to rely on tactile co-ordination and verbal collaboration, making mutual dependence unavoidable. The shared sensory limitation reframed interaction as a practice of collective adaptation and negotiated movement.

*Figure 22: Creating the immersive atmosphere of darkness.
Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.*

Importantly, Socorro's approach to the issue of disability inclusion could be seen as deliberately antagonistic and confrontational. At the conclusion of the piece, when the audience-participants have inevitably failed to assemble the jigsaw puzzle, the artist shouts a barrage of ableist abuse at them as they leave the theatre space. This is indicative of a broader intent to generate moments of disorientation and frustration, deliberately unsettling habitual ways of perceiving and navigating space. Through the creation of this challenging scenario, the performance invited participants to reflect on the everyday obstacles faced by people with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairments, translating lived experience into a shared, affective encounter rather than a representational exercise.

3.10. *Laboratório Pontes / Bridges Laboratory (Rô Colares)*

This project explores the hidden history of urban spaces by treating the city as a series of physical and historical layers. Through an interactive installation, participants engage with ancestral technologies and the concept of a 'Buried Belém' by building and deconstructing a modular structure. This tactile experience forces the audience to negotiate space and balance with one another, turning the act of navigation into a social dialogue. Ultimately, the work aims to deepen the public's

Figure 23: Rô Colares facilitates her performance.
 Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

responsibility rather than an individual task. Through this process, the work reactivated a mode of movement based on mutual adjustment and corporeal agreement, temporarily suspending distance and isolation in favour of collective, democratic, bridge-building between artist and audience.

The image opposite gives an indication of how the project challenged participants to engage in a physically demanding way with their environment and the materials provided, bringing them into visceral bodily contact with the ground beneath their feet. In the process of enacting the work, participants were prompted to navigate and negotiate the use of space to construct a shared installation that they could use as a platform for

connection to urban transit and heritage by making the history of the streets a tangible, shared experiment.

The workshop was grounded in Rô Colares' personal memory of growing up in the Bairro do Telégrafo Sem Fio, a floodplain neighbourhood in Belém shaped by the displacement of Indigenous, riverine, and extractivist communities and by precarious infrastructures built over water. Drawing on the embodied knowledge formed through navigating narrow, unstable wooden bridges during her childhood, the performance translated this lived experience into a collective spatial practice.

Participants were guided through stages of increasing complexity — first moving individually, then in pairs, and finally in groups of four — requiring them to continually negotiate balance, timing, and passage with one another. Progression between these stages was signalled by the artist, reinforcing negotiation as a shared

Figure 24: Participants building together. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

collective movement. The project enabled relational interaction by requiring participants to physically balance and navigate shared structures, transforming movement into a continuous act of mutual adjustment. Progress through the space depended on collective timing and agreement, foregrounding co-operation as a bodily practice.

3.11. *Convite Pará se jogar na cena / Invitation to Immerse Yourself in the Scene* (Thomaz Barbeiro)

Figure 25: Thomaz Barbeiro facilitating his performance. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

This project introduces a creative method called ‘photolarp’, in which participants are invited to step outside of their own identities by merging photography with live-action role-playing. The exercise begins with a small group capturing an image of people in a public setting, which then serves as the foundation for a theatrical intervention.

By using a specific prompt or question provided by the artist, the participants dramatize the captured scene, transforming a static photograph into a lived, improvisational performance. The work functions as a structured invitation to ‘live as others’, using the lens of a camera to bridge the gap between observation and embodied storytelling.

The ‘photolarp’ process generated relational interaction by requiring participants to collectively interpret and activate a captured image, negotiating roles, spatial composition, and timing. Observation became participatory through shared improvisation and embodied

co-authorship. What begins as a moment of looking is gradually transformed into a shared responsibility for action, as participants must agree on how the captured image is activated, sustained, and spatially composed.

Agency is exercised not only through individual bodily choices, but through continuous negotiation with others regarding timing, proximity, rhythm, and intention. In this way, the work links representation to participation, revealing how social situations are not merely depicted but actively produced through coordinated movement and mutual attunement. The method foregrounds performance as a relational practice, in which stepping into another’s position becomes an embodied experiment in co-presence, effort, and shared authorship.

The image opposite shows the participants re-staging the everyday interaction of asking for directions, whilst also playfully recycling everyday objects to create a sense of the flowing movement of traffic moving through the city. The ‘photolarp’ process thus operates as a connective tissue between observation, imagination, and embodied negotiation, extending the photographic act into a collective performative inquiry.

Figure 26: Participants re-staging a scene from the street life of the city. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

In reflecting on his experience of the DRIFT residency, Thomaz Barbeiro spoke positively about the invitation to produce more physically demanding work: ‘*this intensity of the body...body art. For me, this is something that demands more. I like it, challenging myself. That's also something that made me go to another place, as an artist*’ (Barbeiro, 2025).

3.12. Encontro obrigatório anual de jardinagem urbano / Mandatory annual urban gardening event & Reforestamento / Reforestation (Palhaça Catraca)

Figure 27: Ida Luciana Delaude facilitates her performance in the role of Palhaça Catraca. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

Working with her alter-ego, the Clown persona Palhaça Catraca, artist Ida Luciana Delaude created two performance pieces during the DRIFT residency. The *Reforestation* performance was an activity to be performed in pairs, featuring a simple gardening exercise that prompted reflection about who owns the land in the city.

The Mandatory Annual Urban Gardening Event features Palhaça Catraca as a Clown Professor who is engaged in environmental research but has already lost hope for humanity. Participants

attend a brief, melancholic, lesson on urban gardening and its positive effects in mitigating global warming and receive a certificate for their participation.

The image below illustrates how Palhaça Catraca playfully lampoons the typical format in which the narrative of climate emergency is presented in settings like COP30 through abstract diagrams on screens. In contrast with this dispassionate mode of storytelling, the clown invites participants to come together and engage in a ‘hands on’ fashion with the possibilities of urban gardening as a practical method of constructively addressing climate change.

Prior to taking part in the lesson, the artist required participants to dress themselves in multiple layers of winter clothing, gradually adding coats and heavy garments before the class began. In the intense heat of Belém, this action deliberately placed participants in a state of growing physical discomfort as body temperature increased with each additional layer. Once situated in this overheated condition, participants were invited to attend the gardening lesson, effectively experiencing climate change on their own skin.

By mobilising heat, weight, and restricted bodily comfort as dramaturgical tools, the performance transformed abstract discussions of global warming into a visceral, embodied experience, encouraging participants to rethink environmental collapse not as distant data, but as an immediate, lived reality.

The work enabled relational interaction by combining shared discomfort with collective practical action, inviting participants to confront climate change as a co-experienced bodily condition. Gardening became a collaborative gesture, shifting spectatorship into shared ecological responsibility.

Figure 28: The clown professor teaches audience-participants about climate change. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

3.13 Imersão as tradições amazônicas em dança / Immersion in Amazonian Dance Traditions (Xifu Ribiero)

This project invites participants to engage with the vibrant dance traditions and rhythmic heritage of the Amazonian region of Pará. By utilizing a silent disco format that forbids verbal speech, the experience fosters a unique connection rooted entirely in synchronized movement and shared audio. The piece removed the traditional gap between observer and performer, transforming the audience into the active heart of the piece, with a specific focus on allowing audiences from outside the Amazon

Figure 29: Xifu Ribiero observes his performance unfolding. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

region to inhabit a non-verbal communal space, mirroring the ways that local people relate to their own cultural legacy.

The image below shows the work in development during the DRIFT residency. Participants were prompted to connect with each other in performing synchronised movements and, as the picture indicates, some individuals were more confident than others in performing the traditional movements and gestures of Amazonian dance traditions. However, the structure of the work invited participants to learn from each other through observation and imitation.

The performance foregrounded the agency of participants by inviting them to inhabit a rhythm and movement vocabulary that was often unfamiliar to them. While many participants did not possess prior technical knowledge of Amazonian dance forms, they nonetheless followed the audio instructions and rhythmic cues, allowing themselves to experiment, adapt, and respond in real time. This process generated a fluid social choreography in which participants spontaneously formed pairs, trios, and larger groups, joining and separating as they danced, each according to their own physical capacities and interpretive choices. Rather than enforcing uniformity or technical accuracy, the work embraced difference, allowing multiple ways of moving to co-exist simultaneously. In doing so, the performance reframed participation not as the mastery of a specific cultural form, but as an embodied negotiation between guidance and freedom, where learning, imitation, and individual expression unfolded collectively through movement.

In reflecting on his participation in the DRIFT residency, Xifu Ribiero commented on the power of removing himself as a performer and creating a space where audience members could connect with each other: *“I saw that there’s a very powerful side to my artistic work*

Figure 30: Participants engage with each other through synchronised movement. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

that I didn't know - to think about art and not being present while the work is happening. In this role, the audience isn't there to watch you, but to experience your work... it's also a very good experience for relating to other people. A very good experience for dialoguing with your peers or non-peers. With people you know. With people you don't know" (Ribeiro, 2025).

3.14. Tudo Está Queimando / Everything is Burning (ZU-UK and Bruno BO MC)

Figure 31: A trio of participants in *Tudo Está Queimando / Everything is Burning*. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

This piece challenges a world that worships the visual, offering instead a sonic, tactile, and relational way of being together. *Tudo Está Queimando* unfolds inside a shifting landscape of storm and silence.

Using bone-conducting headphones which allow sound to travel through skull and skin — the piece offers an intimate but visceral experience that blurs the boundary between hearing and touch. Players move between intense storm sequences and moments of calm, making decisions that shape how, and whether, they endure.

The performance offers a corrective to a culture built on visual dominance, asking

what it means to navigate the world when the eyes are no longer in charge. It explores how sound, vibration, and proximity can become new forms of trust, attention, and care. The work is a response to the diminishing prospects for the planet and the strange new rituals emerging in an age of catabolic collapse, when systems break down faster than they can be rebuilt. It asks what kinds of listening might sustain us in the dark, and how we might play our way through grief for the world we are losing.

The experience foregrounded the agency of participants by requiring them to actively negotiate both space and social relations under conditions of sensory limitation. Deprived of visual reference points, participants were compelled to adapt their modes of navigation, relying instead on tactile contact, sound cues, and bodily proximity to orient themselves within the environment. Trust became a provisional and continuously renegotiated resource: while some participants formed alliances quickly, establishing temporary partnerships to move through the space, these relationships remained unstable as the game-like structure of this larp-adjacent experience introduced obstacles

Figure 32: Relational bonds through shared risk. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

that disrupted certainty and coordination. As conditions shifted, participants were repeatedly required to recalibrate their reliance on one another, testing the durability of emerging bonds. In this way, the work framed relationality as an active, embodied process shaped by uncertainty, where care and co-operation are not assumed, but continually re-established through sensory attunement and shared risk.

As the images above illustrate, the performance challenges audience-participants to forge strong bonds of trust as they seek a pathway through darkness towards survival. The work enabled relational interaction by placing participants in conditions of shared sensory limitation, where trust and co-operation had to be actively negotiated in real time. Relational bonds formed and dissolved through collective risk-taking, making care an emergent and contingent practice rather than a predefined outcome.

3.15. Jurema (Edivânia Câmara Iyatunde)

Figure 33 Edivânia Câmara Iyatunde in Jurema. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

This performance piece uses the mythical significance of the Jurema plant, which holds a prominent place in Amazonian rituals. The piece seeks to bridge the gap between ancient ecological wisdom and modern urban life. The narrative centres upon Jurema as a leaf-covered spirit who emerges from the wilderness to confront human beings with probing questions about their impact on nature.

Over the course of the DRIFT residency, Edivânia Câmara Iyatunde explored a ritual of symbolic

transformation in which participants were turned into either the forest itself or its guardians, forcing a physical and emotional reckoning with the reciprocity required for healing.

The image opposite shows the piece in development, with participants invited to take part in a ritual that brought them in contact with Jurema. The picture indicates how simple objects like branches could serve as tools to draw participants into the shared creation of the performance. In discussing her participation in DRIFT, Iyatunde commented that the *'intensity'* of the residency had allowed her to *'deconstruct'* her typical working habits and explore new directions in her work through the opportunity for rapid collaboration with other artists (Iyatunde, 2025).

Figure 34: Ritual performance in Jurema. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

The final performance was structured around three simple instructions offered to participants: to approach Jurema's mouth in order to listen to her posing the question: *'What hurts you?'*; to write their response directly onto Jurema's body; and to place one hand on Jurema while resting the other on the body of the participant beside them. Accompanied by the steady sound of a *tambor* resonating through the space, these actions generated the potency of a collective ritual formed around Jurema, who lay at the centre of a darkened room. Following a signal from the facilitator, participants were removed from the space one by one, a gradual withdrawal that reinforced the intimacy and ceremonial nature of the encounter. The ritual structure facilitated relational interaction by linking personal testimony to collective gesture, requiring participants to physically connect while responding to a shared question. The act of touching both the performer and each other established a temporary embodied network of reciprocity and shared reflection.

3.16. Summary

Taken together, the projects developed during DRIFT demonstrate that lowering barriers to participation does not require the removal of structure, but rather the careful calibration of structure. Across the works, we see recurring strategies: the use of **simple but precise instructions**; the creation of **bounded fictional frames**; the mobilisation of **sensory immersion**; and the foregrounding

of **relational care** as the central action of the performance. Importantly, participation was not framed as expressive freedom without limits, but as **agency exercised within designed constraints**. This balance between guidance and openness appears to be a crucial condition for inclusive participatory practice, and it is this tension that the following section explores through the responses of audience-participants.

4. Audience-participant responses to the performances of DRIFT artists

The DRIFT residency brought a group of artists together from a range of creative disciplines and presented them with the common task of designing a piece of performance work that would facilitate interactions between audience-participants. The primary focus on making work based on relations between members of the audience, or participant group, challenged many of the artists with performative backgrounds to shift their attention away from their own performance. Instead, their artistic endeavours were concentrated on devising instructions, prompts, or performative frameworks that would facilitate the relational performances of audience-participants. Throughout the DRIFT residency, artists were given opportunities to test their instructional prompts for participatory performance on a daily basis, using feedback from their peers and mentors to inform ongoing development of the work. Subsequently, at the conclusion of the residency, the performances were presented to members of public whose participation was integral to the final outcomes of the work.

This section of the report for Work Package 4 of Larpocracy centres upon the responses of audience-participants to the work of DRIFT artists, which serve to illuminate our thinking about how larp and larp-adjacent practices may lower barriers to participation and support the construction of cultural spaces for democratic engagement. Our discussions of audience-participant responses will consider the reactions of members of the public alongside more specific analysis of the feedback offered by DRIFT artists when testing the work-in-progress of their peers. A central point of concentration in this section is the nature of the instructions that DRIFT artists devised to guide participation in their performances. The provision of instructions can lower barriers to participation by giving less confident audiences a clear understanding of what they are expected to do, but this provision of guidance carries the risk of excessively controlling the performance and limiting the creative agency of the people who enact the work.

Audience-participant responses were gathered through a combination of informal post-performance conversations, facilitated group reflections, and targeted follow-up interviews focused on moments of relational intensity observed during the performances. Rather than treating audience feedback as evaluative commentary on artistic quality, we approach these responses as indicators of how design decisions either enabled or inhibited participation. In line with the core focus of Larpocracy on democratic engagement, our attention is directed not towards whether participants ‘enjoyed’ the

works, but towards how they navigated instruction, discomfort, collaboration, and relational negotiation within the performative frames provided.

Aside from facilitation instructions, the responses of audience-participants highlight the power of theatrical modes of presentation, with particular emphasis on immersive forms of performance that use the sensory apparatus of theatre to imaginatively transport people to different fictional contexts. Arguably, though, the most striking audience-participant reactions from DRIFT performances were linked to performances that combined a clear framing of the event, often through specific theatrical means, with prompts for participation that centred upon relational care. The gestures of care described are not necessarily harmonious and comfortable. Instead, they often serve to highlight latent social tensions, gender norms and status hierarchies, prompting the people involved to reflect carefully on the political themes of the works in question.

Before turning to the specific themes emerging from audience-participant responses, it is important to situate these observations within the particular conditions of the COP30 context. The work was developed in the lead-up to COP30 in Belém, a moment characterised by heightened global attention to climate justice, alongside localised political, social, and infrastructural pressures. This context both expanded and complicated the conditions for participation. On the one hand, the proximity to COP30 generated increased curiosity, urgency, and openness among participants encountering climate-linked artistic work. On the other hand, the intensity of the surrounding political moment, combined with uneven access conditions and varying levels of familiarity with participatory performance formats, introduced additional thresholds that the projects needed to navigate. The observations that follow should therefore be read not only as reflections on the works themselves, but as situated evidence of how larp-adjacent methodologies operate under conditions of heightened civic and ecological attention. Notably, several of these dynamics were intensified by the COP30 context, suggesting that moments of heightened civic attention may both lower and reshape barriers to participation in larp-adjacent formats.

In the lead-up to COP30, local audience dynamics in Belém were shaped by a degree of public ambivalence towards the event. Informal conversations with local residents and partners indicated that while COP30 brought increased international attention, it also generated concern regarding pressure on already limited urban infrastructure and uneven distribution of anticipated benefits. This context affected how participatory cultural activity was encountered locally, requiring the DRIFT team to work carefully through trusted institutional and community partners to build confidence and accessibility. These conditions underscore the importance of our focus in Work Package 4 of Larpocracy on lowering barriers to participation within complex civic environments rather than assuming that larp or larp adjacent works will be undertaken in a neutral or uniformly receptive audience context.

4.1. Challenges of Instructional Design

In designing instructions for participatory performance, a central method offered by the artists of ZU-UK is the use of audio instructions delivered via headphones as a means of delivering prompts for participatory action, and scaffolding interactions through reassurance and guidance. One of the DRIFT artists, Xifu Ribiero, whose creative background was largely centred upon music and dancing, chose to draw upon headphones as a tool for guiding the actions of participants and one of his initial test sessions led to a number of interesting reflections from other DRIFT artists on the tension between instructions as enabling or restricting. The play test in question featured a tango dance activity which asked two participants to dance together, following audio instructions that guided their steps. One of the dancers, A, commented that:

In this specific proposal, I think the instructions were a little rigid, you know? So, it's okay, uh, it's okay that I needed to follow along and all that, but I thought it was a very step-by-step thing, you know? The dance wasn't a fluid thing for me. After I understood what I was doing, that it was a dance and what the style of that dance was, I was able to understand it and then do it in a more intuitive way, not necessarily just through the insight of the instruction, right? (A, 2025b).

A went on to discuss that she had pre-existing experience as a dancer and, as a result, what she saw as the rigidity of the instructions presented an impediment to her desire for intuitive movement. It might be argued that Xifu's instructions presented a simplicity that might make the activity accessible for novice dancers, but A's comments highlight that instructional guidance can also manifest as restriction to agential expression. Rather than a binary choice between sparse or detailed instructions, it is often a nuanced combination of instructional modes that meets the artist's objectives for their intended relational design.

In another audio-guided performance piece for two participants, which was designed by Yaci Uaruá, the play testers gave further insight into the possible restrictions of instructional guidance. One participant, C, recounted her perception that the audio instructions were delivered at a very quick tempo which might have caused her partner to become stuck and unable to respond:

Because the stimulus from the narrative was very fast when she spoke. Then you already had to react. And in my perception, I already had to react to what I was supposed to do, and then she didn't have a reaction. (C, 2025).

In discussing her experience of this exercise, C's co-player, L, did not directly comment on the tempo of the instructions as being an obstacle to her participation. Instead, she stated that the content of the instructions, which required her to undertake confrontational actions within a fictional role-play scenario, centring upon the breakdown of a relationship, asked her to do things that she did not want to do:

The exercise requires me to engage in conflict with someone. So, I have difficulty carrying on discussions, especially with people I don't know. So, the person in the exercise, they were lying to me. In fact, they said they were lying to me. It was part of the exercise...And initially my

reaction was to play my role and say that this conflict existed, but soon after I wanted to appease, okay? I wanted to say, like, that everything was fine, that everything was okay, that I understood the situation... And then a minute passed, the narrator says that I have to, that it's like, it's part of it, to confront player B. And that's when it got difficult...I'm having this discussion, and since I'm forced to confront player B, Socorro, I have to invent arguments: 'The person told me this, said that, where did they get that reason from?' And then I end up having to pull out a bunch of uncomfortable situations like that, to throw at player B, which is something I personally wouldn't like, but I understood what the idea was. I understood, and I got into the story at that moment because I knew it would end soon...I really wanted to participate, genuinely, I wanted to be there, and I knew that discomfort was precisely what the work wanted to cause. (L, 2025).

As these comments indicate, L's experience was characterised by a commitment to following the instructions, based on an understanding that the scenario was intended to generate conflict, despite the fact that she did not want to enter into a conflictual interaction. It would not be accurate to suggest that L was coerced into participating, but her observations do highlight an ethical tension that is inherent in performances that are based on specific modes of instructional guidance that might cause unintended responses from the participants. L seemed to feel obligated to play her part in the performance, to not let her partner, or the artist, down, but this required her to take actions that caused her to experience discomfort.

In contrast with performances that featured specific instructions on what participants were required to do, several of the DRIFT artists developed works that featured more open-ended prompts for participation. For example, Bruna Almeida's piece invited audience-participants to play a range of childhood games together and connect the activity with nostalgic reflections on the past. In commenting on this piece, public participants noted that their role was challenging, requiring them to rely on their own improvisatory skills, with the possible implication that they had to take on too much responsibility for the progression of the performance. In other performances, public audiences commented that even when instructions are quite specific, the range of interpretations that different people can have of a given instruction can create difficulty. Lu Bórges' performance prompted audience-participants to feed each other, which caused some audience members to voice uncertainty about how to execute the task, while participants in Xifu's Ribeiro's final work, which again featured the synchronised movement of pairs of dancers, noted that the same instruction can be heard differently and enacted differently by two different people, making it almost inevitable that the activity will have some degree of asynchrony.

It should be noted that the challenges that are inherent in following instructions need not be seen as negative features in the works described above. Instead, we argue that a great part of the pleasure of participatory performances works (especially in the early stages of design and testing) lies in space of possibility that comes from interpreting prompts for participation, and it is often the simplest prompts that offer the most scope for interpretive play, whilst still providing a framework to guide participatory action. For example, the performance piece of Bruno BO MC challenged participants to create a rap

in pairs, offering a small number of words to each person along with the task of using the words in simple rhymes. Public audiences commented that their initial apprehensions about rapping with a partner were dissipated by the simplicity of the call to action and some noted that they were motivated to write more verses once they had established a baseline level of confidence with some basic rhymes. In other words, the challenge of instructional design for participatory performance lies in finding the balance between simplicity and structure: participants need parameters to frame their creative actions, but these constraints should not become so specific that they impose rigidity or force people into scenarios that are unpleasant for them.

The tensions described above suggest that instructional design in participatory performance must be understood as a political as well as artistic act. Too little structure may privilege those already confident in self-expression, while overly prescriptive instruction risks reproducing hierarchical control. Lowering barriers to participation therefore requires not the elimination of constraint, but the careful design of constraints that scaffold confidence without suppressing interpretive agency. The findings from DRIFT indicate that simplicity, clarity, and adaptability in instruction are more effective than either total openness or rigid scripting.

4.2. Relational difficulty and acts of care

As we have noted in the previous section, the instructions that stimulate participatory performances are often intentionally challenging in nature and the difficulties that audience-participants face can serve as useful prompts for acts of care. In Yaci Uaruá's piece about a couple experiencing relationship breakdown, L clearly encountered difficulty with the task of performing confrontation, leading her to become 'stuck' in the words of her play partner, C. When asked to describe how she could sense this experience of being stuck, C, who is visually impaired, highlighted a rigidity in L's body which she could feel because she was holding her hand. C went on to discuss how she tried to introduce greater relaxation in the performance by initiating movement, along with ongoing physical contact, to counter her partner's apparent stiffness:

So, I wanted to feel everything that I was hearing from the instruction, right? Because I felt L was very stiff...and then bringing this body, or activating the body at that moment, so that everything would flow...It's partly from my own communication, starting to perceive the other person in this interaction, because I stay for a while and the person doesn't respond right away. So, why isn't she responding? Because I'm looking at her. And then she doesn't respond verbally because I believe she was receiving the audio a little later. It was like a question and answer session. So, while one of us was responding, the other person asked, and the question wasn't the same as the one I had just answered in the text during that conversation, and she was already giving a different answer, so there was a conflict. Right? So, at that moment, I end up having to communicate. So, that's how I communicate with people. (C, 2025)

C went on to observe that by initiating a communication through movement she started to observe her partner joining the physical action which, in her view, made it easier for L to participate in the performance:

In some way, the dialogue flowed from the middle to the end, when I think I passed this on to her, I mean, becoming more (Socorro indicates physical movement)... it's like we trust the person there, you're trying to bring the person closer to you, and the person is still moving around trying to find that trust, you know? Then your body relaxes a little more. It doesn't just wait for the person to react again, right? It already sees that the person has already reacted...at that moment I also notice that her body is moving more. (C, 2025).

As this example suggests, the difficulty of entering into a physical interaction with an unfamiliar person in a performance event can induce a great deal of physical tension for some participants. Rather than seeing this relational difficulty as a negative aspect of the work, we argue that it can serve to stimulate acts of care like C's endeavour to communicate through a combination of touch and movement that might offer greater relaxation to her partner.

The awareness of care as a central concern of participatory performance was also apparent in the development of Xifu Ribiero's tango piece, which was discussed in the previous section. One of the participants, R, mentioned that he was very conscious of the need to maintain a care, or caution, in his physical interactions with his partner, A, since she was a younger woman. R said that he felt a great deal of tension due to his unfamiliarity with tango dancing and went on to say that *'it was also the relationship with a woman I don't know...so I didn't know if I could bother her with some touch or something like that'*. (R, 2025) R elaborated on his hesitancy in approaching his partner by saying that:

Figure 35: Participants dancing tango. Photograph by University of Greenwich / ZU-UK research team.

I think it's because of the care I take when dealing with women, knowing the situations. That happens, you know, in situations like this, like, let's take an artistic residency, men sometimes take advantage to, you know, to play differently... I'm very careful about that. So, as a man, I think we generally have to be careful. And that's where my attention starts. (R, 2025)

As this indicates, care can manifest as physical caution as well as a desire to provide physical support, but in the much the same way that L's hesitancy was addressed by C's touch and movement, in R's case, his partner A responded to caution with a form of care that was confident or even commanding. The audio guidance that Xifu Ribiero offered asked one of the players to put their hand on their partner's shoulder and the other partner to put their hand on the other person's waist. A responded to this instruction by

choosing to counter the traditional gender roles of tango, which would conventionally have the female dancer place their hand on the male dancer's shoulder, and place her hand on R's waist, which transformed her approach to the activity from hesitancy to confidence:

Normally there's a feminine and masculine role within this context, but since I didn't know R – well, I didn't know who he was. So, I played the role of putting my hand on his waist. So, in a way, it was an interesting moment in terms of the access we had to each other's bodies, since he was a complete stranger at that moment...if I had been touched first, I probably would have felt uncomfortable, right? In this context of being a stranger and also being a man, right? So, uh, for me it was important to have this action of being there in command of that physical interaction. (A, 2025b)

A's assertion that she had taken command of the interaction might seem to have negative connotations in terms of dominating the exchange. However, we suggest that the relational difficulty of A's engagement with R usefully prompted care through a mutual generosity in which Bruno took care when physically approaching his partner and A took care by choosing to take command of the exchange. This points towards the idea that acts of care in participatory performance works need not always be soft and gentle, they can also be proactive and strong, in line with A's leadership of the tango and C's guidance of her physical interactions with L. What is particularly notable about these acts of care is that they both appear to invert traditional hierarchies. In the case of R and A, the convention that the man leads the dance was inverted, while in C's case, the fact that she had a visual impairment, which might ordinarily be understood as disability, was the very thing that enhanced her sensitivity to communication through touch and movement, leading her partner to a greater sense of relaxation and comfort.

As the DRIFT residency progressed towards the final public performances, several artists developed works with a strong focus on bodily care. Azeda Pororoça's piece *Banho / Bath* featured an intimate invite-only ritual in which the artist was ceremonially bathed by women audience-participants. In reflecting on the experience, several audience members commented on how moving this act of care was, particularly when they performed it alongside other female family members who had bathed and cared for them in the past. Edivânia Câmara Iyatunde's piece, *Jurema*, also featured a performance of funeral rite which featured the artist's partially naked body as a central focal point. Audience-participants were invited to touch the body, which prompted one audience member to comment on the way that the event had been facilitated to create a sense of ease about nudity and respectful co-presence between the body of the performer and the public participants. A notable aspect of this piece was that it transferred the attention of audiences from the notion of care as concern for the performer's body to a wider consideration of care for the natural world. Audience members discussed Jurema's naked body as a symbol for the death of nature, prompting reflections on the harm that had been done to her. A similar correlation between care for the performer's body and an awareness of care for the environment was stimulated by Lu Bórges' piece *Refeed de Piranha / Piranha Stew*. Audiences commented on the very obvious presence of the performer's body on the dinner table, in relation to the food that they were eating, with one audience member noting their awareness that they

were eating a body (of a shrimp) that was essentially the same as the human body on the table. In other words, the experience of caring, or desiring to care, for the bodies of performers in DRIFT performances encouraged participants to think more broadly about acts of care that could be restorative for the natural world and begin to undo some of the harm that has been done.

The moments of relational difficulty discussed above reveal that participation is not synonymous with comfort. Instead, participatory works may generate productive friction that calls forth acts of care, adjustment, and mutual attunement. In several instances, participants responded to confusion, asynchrony, or emotional discomfort by increasing physical sensitivity to one another, negotiating pace, tone, and proximity. Such micro-gestures of adjustment can be understood as embodied democratic practices: listening, responding, compromising, and sustaining relation under imperfect conditions. Rather than eliminating difficulty, effective participatory design appears to transform difficulty into an opportunity for relational skill-building.

4.3. Immersive theatricality and performative risk

An important feature of many of the performances of DRIFT artists was the use of theatrical tools to create immersive experiences that exerted powerful affects on the bodies of audiences. As noted in the previous section, Iyatunde's piece, *Jurema*, featured a death ritual marked by stillness and quiet, and it was clear that the production of a hushed atmosphere supported a delicate and respectful response from participants. An even more striking example of theatrical immersion can be found in Socorro Lima's work *Zoom Festa da Aparelhagem / Zoom Sound System Party* which plunged the audience into darkness and challenged them to reassemble a jigsaw puzzle. This obviously impossible task presented participants with a tangible experience of being unsighted and expected to carry out a complex task without support, prompting several audience members to reflect on contemporary discourses of inclusion and question whether the efforts to include differently-abled bodies are anywhere near to being sufficient. In a similar vein to the physical challenge that Socorro confronted audiences with, Ida Luciana Delaude's performance of *Encontro obrigatório anual de jardinagem urbano / Mandatory Annual Urban Gardening Event* asked participants to face the consequences of climate change in a very literal way by wearing multiple layers of clothes. Audience members commented on the very real experience of sweltering heat within this experience and linked the performance to the actual climactic conditions in the Amazon region of Brazil that are increasingly inhospitable for the people who live there.

As these examples show, several DRIFT artists used powerful theatrical techniques of sound (or silence), lighting (or darkness) and costume to produce impactful works that immersed the bodies of audiences in particular atmospheres. Alongside the arguable benefits of theatrical immersion, however, several of the performance works indicated possible risks of remaining within the theatrical paradigm of performance with, or for, an audience. In L's account of her experience of Yaci Uaruá's piece, she noted that she was aware of being observed in the performance space, commenting that *'there were other people in the room. Even though I was there, I was being watched by other people...'*

noticed, I felt the gaze' (L, 2025). This awareness of the gaze of external viewers, despite not being gathered as a formal audience in this case, clearly contributed to L's feeling of discomfort in the performance and her initial desire for the activity to end as quickly as possible. A somewhat different example of audience awareness can be found in R's discussions of Xifu Ribiero's tango dance piece, in which he noted that the presence of an audience was a central feature of his experience. At the start of the activity, he commented on his attempt to block out the presence of an audience:

I wasn't looking, I was trying to focus, to concentrate, so, using an artist's technique, right? Creating the audience as a single mass so as not to perceive the individual reactions. So, I've done that as a musician my whole life, and at that moment I did it more than ever. So, I didn't care much about the audience in order to focus, right? (R, 2025).

R went on to describe how he started to make mistakes when his headphones started to malfunction, meaning that he was unable to follow the dance instructions, which caused the audience to laugh. Rather than treating this as a negative experience, R started to play to the crowd and took enjoyment in their enjoyment of his failure:

I had to be synchronized and then I wasn't receiving the instructions. So, then I was already hearing the laughter, the, you know, the reactions of the audience. At that moment I was seeing more of the audience's reaction because I wasn't able to hear the instructions...I was confused, but then the tension decreased because then I became more like, it was funnier. Then I relaxed a bit because I was making mistakes and it was funny that naturally, as a dancer, I was going to make even more mistakes without having instructions. So, I found myself once again in a comical situation involving dance, which is something I've done many times in my life. Then I felt more relaxed, like, I don't know, like a comedian who was there trying to dance and like a foreigner dancing samba. (R, 2025).

Notwithstanding the fact that R came to enjoy his comedic performance, he acknowledged that this caused a shift in focus away from his partner. Initially, he stated that his attention was '*only the partner*' but when he started to relax in response to audience laughter, he said that his attention was transferred to the '*gimmicks*' of the theatre that would allow him '*to be the funny one*' (R, 2025). This example indicates that even when participants enjoy being watched by an audience, the feeling of needing to entertain external viewers can be an unhelpful impediment to forming a connection with other people who are taking part in the activity.

Aside from performances that utilised theatrical means, a number of DRIFT projects featured more low-key activities based on everyday experiences and interactions. Thomaz Barbeiro's piece *Convite Pará se jogar na cena / Invitation to Immerse Yourself in the Scene* challenged participants to observe an ordinary piece of social interaction in the streets of Belém and provide a simple reconstruction of this interaction. In reflecting on this experience, audience members commented on the value of being invited to notice everyday activities of the city, like noticing a person scavenging for trash that they could salvage to make some money and highlighted the potential of having an actual connection to such experiences by producing their creative reconstruction within the urban environment itself.

Another example of a relatively simple performance was Mariô Monteiro's piece *Enquanto a música toca / While the Music Plays*, which featured the ritual of a birthday party. In reflecting on this experience, participants responded warmly to the familiar routines of songs and birthday speeches, suggesting that relatively everyday experiences of celebration can provide accessible opportunities for audience participation in performance events.

During the COP30 period, the density of parallel events, debates, and public programming across Belém created both opportunities and challenges for audience engagement. A standalone performance offer would likely have struggled to attract sustained public attention within this highly saturated cultural environment. In response, the DRIFT activities were embedded across multiple partner platforms and venues, including collaborations with Theatre & Dance School of the Federal University of Pará, the university's postgraduate arts venue, British Council networks, events curated by UNLIMITED, Museu das Amazônias, and the Gasômetro cultural complex. This distributed approach significantly broadened audience exposure and enabled the DRIFT artists to encounter both local and international audiences beyond their immediate networks.

Notably, several artists subsequently received invitations for further presentations, commissions, and professional visibility, while partner institutions reported longer-term developments including the establishment of a sensory neurodivergent-friendly space at Museu das Amazônias and ongoing dialogue around inclusive cultural policy frameworks. While these developments extend beyond the immediate scope of our activities within Work Package 4, they indicate the potential for larp-adjacent methods to generate sustained institutional effects when situated within major civic moments such as COP30.

4.4. Summary

To conclude this section of the Work Package 4 report, the response of audience-participants to the performances created by DRIFT artists indicates that barriers to participation in performance works can be lowered by the provision of **simple instructions** that provide enough structure to guide the action whilst also leaving enough space for participants to express their creative agency. The examples cited in this section highlight many instances of difficult participation, but we suggest that **relational difficulty** is not something that should be entirely smoothed away as it often provides a useful **stimulus for participants to support and care for each other**.

We have noted that the tools of **theatrical immersion** can produce powerful affects that shift the embodied state of audience members and, potentially, brings them closer to a felt understanding of what the artist is trying to achieve, but we have also noted the value of offering simple frameworks for interaction and emphasised the risk of maintaining performer-audience relationships that may distract participants in participatory works from meaningfully engaging with each other. In sum, the responses of public participants and DRIFT artists who tested each other's work-in-development suggest that participatory performance-makers are fundamentally **framework providers** and **instructional authors**: creating performative contexts and instructions that stimulate relational

encounters. The instructions that audience-participants are given should be simple but the substance of what they are asked to do does not always have to be easy. Instead, the provocation to cope with **relational difficulty can stimulate gestures of care** that encourage participants to take command of situations, challenge existing hierarchies and foster connection with the other people around them.

The audience responses documented here suggest that larp and larp-adjacent practices can lower barriers to participation when they combine clear framing, accessible entry points, and embodied relational tasks. Participation was most inclusive where audiences were neither abandoned to total improvisation nor tightly controlled by rigid scripting but instead guided through carefully designed prompts that supported confidence while preserving interpretive space. These findings directly contribute to the objective of Work Package 4 to investigate how artistic methods can create more inclusive spaces for democratic engagement.

5. Conclusion

Work Package 4 of the Larpocracy project investigates how larp and larp-adjacent practices can lower barriers to cultural participation, and this report has addressed this question through discussion and analysis of the DRIFT artistic residency, which took place in Belém, in the Pará region of Brazil, in late October and early November 2025. The report has considered how our facilitation of DRIFT set a high barrier to participation for the artists involved by challenging them to engage in an intensive period of developing their work and testing the work of others. The report has illustrated how the artists responded to the core provocation to develop performance works that stimulated **interaction between participants**. Subsequently, our exploration of responses from audience-participants to the artists' performances has pointed towards useful insights on how participatory performance-makers can create accessible and engaging works that simultaneously provoke **relational difficulty alongside acts of care**.

A core characteristic of the DRIFT is the **rapid process of iterating and testing creative ideas**. This approach to an artistic residency not only prompts artists to avoid overthinking their concepts and prioritise the practical functions of work-in-progress. It also encourages the development of a **community of practice founded upon mutual support**, in which artists become a resource for each other by offering feedback that informs the next step in creative development. In a disciplinary context that is strongly influenced by traditions of theatre, we have noted that artists often foreground their performative skills and the immersive atmospheres that theatrical presentation can create, but we have also highlighted the risks of continuing to operate within a theatrical paradigm that reasserts the artistic hierarchy of the performer-audience relationship or makes participants feel self-conscious about being observed by spectators.

The theatrical impulses of DRIFT artists were counteracted by the invitation to experiment with the tools of game design and live action role-play, which challenged them to reconsider their position as

designers of creative instructions that could stimulate the action of audience-participants. Our encouragement of instruction-led performance was also supported by showing previous ZU-UK works, like *Binaural Dinner Date*, as examples of how to create work with a relatively high level of instructional guidance that might enhance accessibility for audience-participants. In arguing for instruction-led performance we have challenged the notion that the unfettered agency of participants is necessarily a good thing, noting that the capacity to express creative agency is privilege that is not equally shared by all. Consequently, by foregrounding the value of instructional guidance that is delivered through methods of facilitation we believe that audience-participants who may feel less confident in expressing themselves within a given work may be supported to engage with the activity rather than stepping back from it.

A notable feature of the examples we have discussed of participant responses to the works of DRIFT artists is the experience of varying forms of **relational difficulty**. We have noted that designing contexts in which audience-participants are prompted to interact and create something together is not necessarily easy, or harmonious, but we do not believe that it should be. In other words, relational difficulty is part of the value of participatory performance, enabling participants to negotiate challenging themes, hierarchical relationships and even the apparently simple acts of being together and touching each other. By presenting people with the challenge of interacting with others within a set of clearly articulated parameters, we argue that participatory performance works can create brave spaces where care can be expressed strongly as **purposeful support and caring guidance**. Consequently, we suggest that our research can usefully point beyond notions of ‘safe’ spaces in which care is something is soft and gentle, towards a more robust approach to designing relational play.

The overall findings from the Working Package 4 report that are set out above can be succinctly summarised in the following list of key insights from this research on how larp and larp-adjacent practices can support cultural participation and democratic engagement:

- Participatory accessibility is most effectively supported through clear but flexible instructional design, which scaffolds confidence without over-determining participant behaviour.
- Relational encounter, rather than performative spectacle, can be understood as the primary mechanism through which audiences engage with participatory performance works.
- Moments of managed difficulty or ambiguity often prompt increased attentiveness, care, and negotiation between participants.
- Instances of heightened civic attention, like the COP30 context, can simultaneously enable and complicate participation, requiring distributed partnership strategies that combine local and international networks to reach diverse audiences beyond existing arts communities.

In presenting this report on the activities of Work Package 4, we acknowledge that our research has not offered substantial evidence of marginalised communities having barriers to cultural participation lowered through their participation in larp, or larp adjacent practices. However, we believe that our initial findings from the DRIFT residency indicate a set of artistic strategies that can be further

developed and tested with individuals and groups who may have suffered from social and political marginalisation. In pursuing this ongoing work, we suggest that the role of the performance facilitator is a key point of focus, serving as care-taker figure who can deliver instructional guidance that simultaneously challenges audience-participants in their interactions without challenging them too much. As noted in the previous section, we see great potential in the archetypal figure of the clown as a facilitator that offers provocation whilst also setting clear parameters for the performance. We also wish to develop our methods and ideas regarding the foundational value of shared movement and physical contact as the basis for interactive connections that can engender productive relational tension, shifting notions of care beyond comfort in the here and now towards strong and purposeful gestures of care.

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